

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RESULTS OF TOTAL KNEE ARTHROPLASTY IN TERMS OF
FUNCTIONAL SCORING AND KNEE SOCIETY SCORING IN
GHURKI TRUST TEACHING HOSPITAL LAHORE****¹Dr Muhammad Kashif, ²Dr Kaleemullah, ³Dr Rehan Wani, ⁴Dr Syed Ahmad Bilal
Bukhari, ⁵Dr Latif Khan, ⁶Dr Khalid Ameer.**^{1,2,3,4,5} FCPS, Senior Registrar Orthopaedics, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore., ⁶FCPS, Consultant
Orthopaedic Surgeon, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To estimate the functional score in patients who underwent total knee replacement before and after surgery.**Place and Duration:** In the Orthopaedic department of Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore for two years duration from October, 2015 to October, 2017.**Method:** An observational cross-sectional study consisting of 40 patients evaluated by a single surgeon in the same configuration for two years follow-up between October, 2015 to October, 2017. Data from the National Joint Registry of Pakistan (PNJR) was collected. The Knee society score was evaluated at 1 year and 2 years follow-up before and after surgery.**Results:** In our study, we analysed a total of 40 patients with 12(30%) males and 28(70%) female patients with mean age of 55.45 9.25 years and age range of 40 to 70 years. Forty-one patients had osteoarthritis in 90% (n = 36) and rheumatoid arthritis in 10% (n = 4). The mean preoperative knee society score was 51.07 ± 13.3 and the preoperative functional score was 42.87 16.4, whereas the postoperative score of the knee society was 91.75 3.44 and 87.32 6.33 was the postoperative functional score.**Conclusion:** For knee arthritis; Total knee arthroplasty is the best method because the scores improved in terms of functional score and knee society.**Key words:** Osteoarthritis, Total knee replacement, knee population score, rheumatoid arthritis.**Corresponding author:****Dr Muhammad Kashif**

FCPS, Senior Registrar Orthopaedics, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore.

dr.kashif276@gmail.com +92-333-5589349

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Kashif et al., **Results Of Total Knee Arthroplasty In Terms Of Functional Scoring In Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Knee arthritis remains a major issue for some time, but (TKR) total knee replacement has modernized the management of knee pain because of arthritis [1]. TKR improves life quality by decreasing pain and increasing mobility in approximately ninety percent of patients [2]. To evaluate the TKR success ratio; various rating scales were used [3]. However, there is a significant alteration between the surgeon's results

and the patient's assessment [4]. Where the patient is not satisfied with the outcome, there may be different opinions and definitions of the best outcome or outcome of the procedure, such as patients and surgeons opinions [5]. The patient may not want to disappoint the surgeon, because he may not be able to tell him his real problem, and if so, the surgeon may not understand the true nature of the patient's pain and dissatisfaction [6].

Functional score pre-operative vs post-operative:

Functional score		Pre-operative	Post-operative	
	Mean $\pm$ SD	42.87 $\pm$ 16.4	87.32 $\pm$ 6.33	
Functional score	81 – 100 (Excellent)	70 – 80 (Good)	60 – 69 (Fair)	Below 60 (Poor)
	N			
Pre-operative	0	03	07	30
Post-operative	29	11	-	-

These scoring systems (including outcome measures assessed by the physician) yielded functional outcome, clinical examination and symptoms in a scoring system (CROM), and these scores hide the opposite dimensions because the subject receives pain, but the range of mobility is improved and also had better muscle strength and functional stability [7]. Total knee replacement measurement represented an improvement in the estimation of TKR results. However, the improvement of the movement and the acceptance of general psychometric principles to improve assessment tools have established new standards for evaluating and measuring clinical evaluation systems. Index community score is easy to use and concise [8]. The functional score of the knee community shows good reliability. Install 1989, introduce the original scoring system of the knee community [9]. At that time, patients who had undergone total knee replacement were immobile, so it would be appropriate to evaluate knee functions based on patients walking and climbing stairs. Nowadays, patients supposing to live extra twenty years after total knee replacement are essential to continue actively participating in routine functional and recreational activities yonder the sedentary lifestyle after the total knee replacement surgery [10]. This study was held in order to know the preoperative and postoperative scores in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and the functional results of TKR in patients

with osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis score in our configuration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This observational cross-sectional study was held in the Orthopaedic department of Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Lahore for two-years duration from October, 2015 to October, 2017. Total knee replacement was performed in patients with knee arthritis including rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis. We included all patients with severe rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis, one or both knees, suffering enough to interfere with daily accomplishments, and wanting total knee replacement. All patients who are not suitable for surgery and are not willing to undergo TKR for other reasons such as heart disease or other diseased systemic conditions. The patient's demographic details such as age, sex, height, diagnosis and comorbidity are documented in the PNJR and calculation requirements such as knee society score range of motion and other evaluations are recorded in the Performa. All the documented procedures were performed in the same operating room by the same surgeon and same protocol by parapataller approach and applying tourniquet midline incision were done under combined spinal epidural anesthesia. Standard tibial and femoral implants were used. In no case patellar implant was used.

Age and comorbid:

Age	
Mean $\pm$ standard deviation	55.45 $\pm$ 9.25
Comorbids	
	N %
HTN	27 (67.5 %)
DM	12 (30 %)
HEPATITIS	4 (10 %)

Linezolid, Sulbactam plus Cefeperazone were used as antibiotics. Epidural analgesia followed by oral analgesia is added with the addition of intravenous analgesia after 48 hours. Mechanical and Chemical thromboprophylaxis was used. The patients were kept under the supervision of physiotherapist on the first postoperative day. Skin sutures were removed on day 14 and followed regularly for six weeks, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year and 2 year. Full examination of patients performed to calculate the knee society score at 1 year. The results are given in tables, percentages and graphs. The mean standard was calculated for variables such as preoperative knee society, age, and postoperative

deviation. Using SPSS version 20.0; the Data were analyzed.

RESULTS:

Of the 40 patients, female were 28(70%) and male were 12(30%). 40 to 70 years was the age range, with 55.45 average age. Of these 40 cases, osteoarthritis was noted in 90% (n = 36), and rheumatoid arthritis in 10% (n = 4); however, previous patients had 30% (n = 12) diabetic, 67.5% (n = 27) hypertensive and hepatitis in 10% (n = 4). ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) 15% (n = 6) cases of grade I, grade II 77.5% (n = 31) and ASA grade III 7.5% (n = 3) patients were noted.

Ambulation status:

The ambulation status was 29 community polyclinics, 7 polyclinics and 4 polyclinics. The follow-up of the patients was 14 days, 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year and 2 year. At one-year follow-up, the mean score

of the knee and ED population was 91.75 ± 3.44 and the mean functional score and SD was 87.32 ± 6.33 . The 29 patients functional score was 81 - 100 (excellent score) and (good score 70 - 80) in 11 cases.

Outcome regarding knee society score:**DISCUSSION:**

For knees arthritis total knee replacement is an effective management and gave outstanding functional results. Patients with mobilization difficulties due to arthritic changes achieved better functional results after TKR. After total knee arthroplasty, there was enhancement in life quality such as pain relief, deformity correction and improved mobility [11]. Although the total knee replacement satisfaction has been determined, the importance of expectation is recorded because TKR is done both for functional development of the joint and for pain relief. The individual goals of each patient, based on outcomes such as improvement of function and activity, will essentially determine how successful the patient's outcome is. In the 1995 study, Gill compared the rheumatoid arthritis (30 knees) and osteoarthritis (37 knees) clinical results and with a 10-year follow-up [12]. All patients had excellent results in rappings of range of motion, decreased pain and stability. In our analysis, knee scoring and functional outcome enhanced and had better outcomes in 29 patients (72.5%) and good functional score in 11 patients (27.5%). The total knee replacement result is evaluated by the knee society score. In our study, an important development was noted in both the knee functional score and knee society score in the clinical and functional improvement evaluation evaluated by CSR. In 2012, Farahini conducted a similar study showing a significant improvement in the knee society score [13]. In another study conducted by Varatapalli 2015, it was observed that there was rise in knee society scores after TKR [14]. Stage RV 2016 studied showed a preoperative knee society score of 50.01 ± 14.09 and increased KSS 86.08 ± 4.94 at six months of

follow-up. In our analysis, preoperative KSS was 50.97 ± 13.2 and it increased to 91.75 ± 3.50 after 1 year follow-up. In the same study, Stage 2016 showed that the functional score was 80%, excellent, good, 12.5%, and positive results were 5%. In our study, 72.5% of the functional scores were excellent and 27.5% gave good results [15].

CONCLUSION:

Total knee replacement is a safe surgery. After total knee replacement; clinical and functional and outcome of the patient improves. The patient's quality of life, such as mobility and pain, is reflected in the scoring system such as the functional scoring system.

REFERENCES:

1. Shriram, Krishnamoorthy, A. B. Govindaraj, A. N. Vivek, Sohanlal VijayKumar, and M. Anand. "Functional outcome of single stage bilateral total knee replacement measured using oxford knee score." *Journal of Arthroscopy and Joint Surgery*(2019).
2. Wilson, Hannah A., Rob Middleton, Simon GF Abram, Stephanie Smith, Abtin Alvand, William F. Jackson, Nicholas Bottomley, Sally Hopewell, and Andrew J. Price. "Patient relevant outcomes of unicompartmental versus total knee replacement: systematic review and meta-analysis." *bmj* 364 (2019): 1352.
3. Ferrera, Hannah K., Todd E. Jones, Natalie J. Schudrowitz, Jamie E. Collins, Paul M. Lichstein, Julie L. Shaner, and Wolfgang Fitz. "Perioperative Dietary Restriction of Carbohydrates in the Management of Blood Glucose Levels in Patients Undergoing Total

- Knee Replacement." *The Journal of arthroplasty* (2019).
4. Biggs, P. R., G. M. Whatling, C. Wilson, and C. A. Holt. "Correlations between patient-perceived outcome and objectively-measured biomechanical change following Total Knee Replacement." *Gait & posture* 70 (2019): 65-70.
 5. Christiansen, Meredith B., Louise M. Thoma, Hiral Master, Dana Voinier, Laura A. Schmitt, Melissa L. Ziegler, Michael P. LaValley, and Daniel K. White. "The feasibility and preliminary outcomes of a physical therapist-administered physical activity intervention after total knee replacement." *Arthritis care & research* (2019).
 6. Girdler, S.J. and Glezos, C.D., 2019. Does Patella Resurfacing Affect Postoperative Blood Loss in Patients Undergoing Total Knee Replacement?. *Techniques in Orthopaedics*.
 7. Fraenkel, Liana, W. Benjamin Nowell, Christine E. Stake, Shilpa Venkatachalam, Rachel Eyler, George Michel, and Ellen Peters. "Impact of Information Presentation Format on Preference for Total Knee Replacement Surgery." *Arthritis Care & Research* 71, no. 3 (2019): 379-384.
 8. Nugent, Mary, Michael C. Wyatt, Christopher M. Frampton, and Gary J. Hooper. "Despite improved survivorship of uncemented fixation in total knee replacement for osteoarthritis, cemented fixation remains the gold standard: an analysis of a National Joint Registry." *The Journal of Arthroplasty* (2019).
 9. Mooney, Luke, Peter L. Lewis, David G. Campbell, Yi Peng, and Alesha Hatton. "Rates and outcomes of total knee replacement for rheumatoid arthritis compared to osteoarthritis." *ANZ journal of surgery* (2019).
 10. Buvanendran, Asokumar, Dan Wang, Hyungsuk Kim, Jeffrey S. Kroin, and Robert J. McCarthy. "RNA expression preoperatively and postoperatively following total knee replacement: a pilot study in patients with and without chronic postsurgical pain." (2019): 246-251.
 11. Barisano, G., Culo, B., Shellock, F.G., Sepelband, F., Martin, K., Stevens, M., Wang, D.J., Toga, A.W. and Law, M., 2019. 7-Tesla MRI of the brain in a research subject with bilateral, total knee replacement implants: Case report and proposed safety guidelines. *Magnetic resonance imaging*, 57, pp.313-316.
 12. Cassuto, Jean, Agnetha Folestad, Jan Göthlin, Henrik Malchau, and Johan Kärrholm. "The key role of proinflammatory cytokines, matrix proteins, RANKL/OPG and Wnt/ β -catenin in bone healing of hip arthroplasty patients." *Bone* 107 (2018): 66-77.
 13. Niu, Chi-Chien, Song-Shu Lin, Li-Jen Yuan, Lih-Huei Chen, Chuen-Yung Yang, An-Ni Chung, Meng-Ling Lu, Tsung-Ting Tsai, Po-Liang Lai, and Wen-Jer Chen. "Correlation of blood bone turnover biomarkers and Wnt signaling antagonists with AS, DISH, OPLL, and OYL." *BMC musculoskeletal disorders* 18, no. 1 (2017): 61.
 14. Friedrich, M.J., Wimmer, M.D., Schmolders, J., Strauss, A.C., Ploeger, M.M., Kohlhof, H., Wirtz, D.C., Gravius, S. and Randau, T.M., 2017. RANK-ligand and osteoprotegerin as biomarkers in the differentiation between periprosthetic joint infection and aseptic prosthesis loosening. *World journal of orthopedics*, 8(4), p.342.
 15. Wang, Jian-Hang, Yuanjin Zhang, Hong-Yan Li, Yun-Yan Liu, and Tao Sun. "Dickkopf-1 negatively regulates the expression of osteoprotegerin, a key osteoclastogenesis inhibitor, by sequestering Lrp6 in primary and metastatic lytic bone lesions." *Medicine* 95, no. 24 (2016).